

The Fab Economy – Economic Governance Design and Digital Infrastructure

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Abstract

In this contribution we develop the contours of a Fab Economy and how it can be implemented with a well-fitting digital infrastructure. We do so by first analysing microeconomic and transaction cost economic characteristics of a “Data-in-Data-out” Fab Economy, where bits circulate globally and atoms circulate locally. Based on this, we derive an economic structure (governance) of the overall Fab Economy at different stages of its value chain. The findings are finally used to define essential success factors that a digital infrastructure must implement so that a Fab Economy can thrive on it.

Keywords

Fab Economy, Circular Economy, Economic Governance, Digital Infrastructure

1 Introduction

In the context of this paper, in 2022, the Fab City-Community is funded by the European Union via the project INTERFACER to develop software for an operating system for Fab Cities - Fab City OS (FCOS). FCOS aims to become an essential layer of the digital infrastructure for Fab Cities and Regions and with it Fab Labs around the world. FCOS is free and open source software that supports value creation across the whole value chain of distributed production, ranging from distributed design to distributed manufacturing, disassembly and recycling. FCOS shall foster efficient and effective data exchange between the different nodes of the Fab Lab and Fab City (Fab) network. Its main technological invention is an extended Digital Product Passport (DPP) which saves each design contribution in the distributed design process on a distributed ledger (blockchain). For an orientation in crypto debates, we state that FCOS is to be understood as a Web3 initiative as Roio (2022) defines the term.

In the latest iteration of the software, all products on FCOS are themselves open or source available, but not necessarily free for economic sale of its physical derivatives. Physical derivatives of the digital design (e.g. build manuals in pdf, CAD, CAM, jpeg, etc. denote the physical products that are being built according to digital design. The basic idea is that if a manufacturer sells the physical derivative, the designers get a share of the price according to their individual contribution saved on the blockchain. This gives the designers financial remuneration for their work on open designs and flips the power relations in the value chain of production upside down. It gives product developers the economic freedom to design for circularity in the product life cycle (longevity, repairability, modularity, recyclability, ...) rather than planned obsolescence (see Seidel & Roio, 2021; Kühn & Seidel, 2022).

Similar to desktop operating systems, FCOS is just one - nevertheless basic - layer of software for Fab Cities and Regions. Within the INTERFACER project, which makes up the initial phase of FCOS development,

already different applications are being developed. The adoption of FCOS creates the basis for a flourishing Fab Economy. It is the ambition that this happens in line with the Fab City vision as envisioned in the main white paper. This paper aims to be a compass for strategy, policy, expectations and implications for and of FCOS.

Economic Governance Design (EGD) is a 21st century version of Walter Eucken's Ordnungspolitik. Eucken's basic insight was that for forming a new economy, one first needs to determine the boundary conditions (Ordnung) on whose basis this new economy shall operate. Only then, Eucken argues, there will be order in the sense of the absence of chaos in the economic system. Specifically, only if all rather detailed decisions on economic regulation have an overall "goal" (order), these decisions will be coherent and not contradictory to each other. Eucken developed his concept as a model for what Germany's general economic order should look like after the centrally planned economy during Fascism. (see Eucken, 1999). Now, confronted with accelerating multiple crises (see Brandt, 2009) and an ongoing technological revolution (see Perez, 2010), the changing overall economic order poses a window of opportunity once more. These circumstances call for what we label a new Economic Governance Design (EGD). The EGD aims to conceptualise the best economic governance for these circumstances, in the sense that the governance design reduces harm of the forces at play to people and the planet. Economic governance is a term used in transaction cost economics (see Benkler, 2002) to analyse economic order. For example, a typical question in economic governance science would be whether, in a given situation, a market or a planned economy is the better economic governance, i.e. order. We add "Design" to it, because not only do we argue for a certain economic governance, but also claim that it can be realised with FCOS. In our following argument we also apply micro economic and institutional economic analysis.

The specific question we pose in this paper is what the overall order or EGD and resulting power distribution of the economy that unfolds on top of the FCOS digital infrastructure shall be. Put differently, this paper develops argumentation for the governance of a Fab Economy, that is, how a Fab Economy could and should look like. Having a picture of this basic order, it will become possible to derive a coherent technical architecture and features as well as overall regulatory implications needed to establish a flourishing Fab Economy.

2 Methodology and Guiding Principles

To argue for a certain order of the economy that shall unfold itself on top of FCOS, we set guiding principles, drawing from economic theory. In terms of economic governance, we draw from transaction cost economics. In terms of power distribution within institutions and networks, our argument is grounded in institutional economics (see Elinor Ostrom, a prominent scholar of the commons). In terms of price policy and price mechanism, we draw from microeconomics.

One of the key methods we apply is based in Transaction Cost Economics (TCE). Transaction costs are the costs of an economic transaction. For example, these can be transportation or bargaining costs as well as fees for blockchain transactions. Once a certain level of transaction costs in an economy is reached, firms (companies) emerge. This was Ronald Coase's (1937) basic insight of his "theory of the firm". The higher the transaction costs in a given economic system, the bigger the firms (companies) will be that are able to sustain/emerge in that economic system. Vice versa, the lower transaction costs become, the smaller the companies in that system become. Building on top of this, Benkler (2002) argues that when transaction costs become extremely low, peer production emerges. For example, it does not take much to contribute to Wikipedia, meaning the transaction costs are low. So through the lense of TCE, Wikipedia is as powerful as it is, because Wikimedia - the digital infrastructure beneath Wikipedia - has dramatically reduced transaction costs of production of encyclopaedia articles. In this paper, we analyse how much a digital infrastructure such as Fab City OS should be able to reduce transaction costs of distributed production in a Fab Economy, at different stages of its value chains. From this analysis, we will be able to derive which economic governance a Fab Economy will be likely to emerge at the different stages of its value chains.

In terms of the price mechanism, we analyse marginal costs, which are the costs that arise when producing an additional unit of a given asset/artefact/product. Thereby, we get a grounded idea on what the prices in the different realms of the economy would be ideally. In microeconomic theory, prices are optimal when they equal marginal costs. In such a theoretical situation, there are no passive rents, meaning income without effort. Therefore, since copying (reproducing) bits (digitised information) is almost free (low marginal costs), its prices would be optimal if they were zero. If prices were zero, there would be no market, but peer production one may argue. In line with this, we invoke the classical theory of value according to which - put simply - human labour is what determines value. So in principle, the more labour is put into a product on FCOS, the higher the exchange value should be. This is an important parameter for the price policy of FCOS.

In terms of power distribution, we adhere to a commons-based governance. This means that, generally speaking, the rules of the network(s) are defined by the network(s) itself (themselves). So, principally, decisions should be made by those who are directly affected by them. Whenever possible and reasonable, decisions are to be made locally. In other words, the principle of subsidiarity applies.

In terms of its overall goal we argue the Fab City aims to establish conditions in which humans can live in dignity. We think human dignity and not other possible highest goals such as social and/or ecological sustainability as the highest goal, because in our understanding, all other goals an economy may aim for must be subordinate to human dignity.

3 Actors and Institutional Setting of the Fab Economy

Following Benkler (2002), transaction costs (transportation costs, negotiation costs, information gathering costs, etc.) are the main factor determining economic governance. The lower the transaction costs, the smaller the economic actors can be that are able to sustain economically. Digital assets, such as construction manuals, on FCOS are free or source available. Therefore, FCOS likely decreases the transaction costs of a circular economy significantly, which levels the advantages of big corporations in the current system. As a result, the users of FCOS are peers, small and medium-sized organisations (SMEs and legal entities representing local Fab Cities and Regions, Fab Labs) and those who are interested in connecting with the FCOS API (e.g. Local Marketplaces). This fits with the Fab network which consists of small economic actors. So, in order to serve these small actors, FCOS and its associated economy should be open and accessible - that is, the threshold to participate should be as low as possible.

We categorise the users of FCOS into five categories:

Fab Cities and Regions

Fab Labs, Designers, Manufacturers, After-Manufacturers and SMEs

End Product Customer

Fab Marketplace Providers

FCOS App Developers

We propose the following institutional setting for developing, maintaining and providing FCOS as the digital infrastructure of the Fab Economy consists of the following institutions:

- Local Fab City's (Region's) Associations: Governing and providing a local Fab City Node is resource intensive and shall eventually be compensated with sales on FCOS.
- The Fab City Foundation (FCF): the FCF owns the Fab City brand and ultimately decides on who and what is part of the overall Fab City network.
- As it is the basic idea of Fab Labs and Fab Cities to reduce access barriers for participation in production, the FCOS code base is a common pool resource, i.e. transaction costs are reduced as much as possible. Theoretically, there could be one FCOS development organisation to develop, maintain and promote FCOS, but it can also be a multitude of organisations or individual developers contributing to the code base. Compliance with local regulation and book keeping of financial and other transactions are an argument for centralization. Numerous scandals in the

context of crypto exchanges and its effects on trust in the respective economy give reason for the FCF to ensure reliability and trustworthiness of the one or more organisations providing the “back-office” infrastructure. A main task is to find appropriate partners to delegate the handling of money flows. Developing and maintaining FCOS software as well as offering support for it, requires resources.

- If FCOS holds what it promises, then it is legitimate to fund this development, maintenance and support through financial cuts (win-win). The aim should be to reach the principle of marginal costs equalling the price, or in other words, to avoid passive rent. Pricing and budget of the FCOS development should be transparent and be made available to the global network. The FCOS development should be non-profit. The brand FCOS should be based on an agreement with the FCF. The agreement should make sure that FCOS always stays connected to the FC Values, controlled by the FCF.

4 A Price Policy and Price Mechanism for the Fab Economy

As stated above, according to microeconomic theory prices are optimal when they equal the marginal cost of production. Our aim is to derive a price policy for a Fab economy. For this we now analyse the marginal costs at different stages of the value chain first.

In the context of FCOS (Open Source Hardware), gaining information that is then digitised in the first place, is significantly more resource and effort intensive, compared with writing encyclopaedia articles for example. Writing an Open Source Hardware (OSH) Documentation (OSHD) is often even more time consuming than developing the physical object. Copying (reproducing) bits (digitised information) is almost free (low marginal costs) so its price is optimal when close to zero, which is the case when accessing global digital assets on FCOS. In manufacturing, after-manufacturing and recycling, marginal costs will always be significantly high. In stages of the value chain where marginal costs are high, prices are therefore high which is albeit appropriate as this compensates for the effort for each additional unit.

Because the contributions to designs require much resources, contributors have high investments. Therefore, FCOS will not only allow free and open source licences for OSHD, but also have so-called Fab Shares (similar to source available software licences). With Fab Shares, designers get the chance to participate financially from the economic usage of their designs later in the value chain. The governance objective of Fab Shares is to give bigger economic actors sufficient incentives to contribute to the global design repository (commons).

Having these preliminary arguments in mind, if we now apply the price=marginal costs it seems that it is not optimal that all hardware documentation is free and open. So FCOS should not have a policy that prohibits sale of hardware documentation. On the contrary, FCOS should invite actors that need compensation for their work. For prices, this means that after the initial effort and an appropriate margin are compensated for, digital assets should be free (price) and open (undisclosed and unrestricted) for economic use.

Most digital resources in the context of OSH require maintenance, which is itself an effort and tendentially legitimate to be compensated. Still, with a growing size and density of the network, the time until the initial investment and an appropriate margin are compensated for, decreases. In the medium term, FCOS aims to be adopted worldwide, which would be a huge network. The bigger the network gets the more digital resources will be free and open for economic utilisation. So, if resources are (re)produced without or with little human labour involved, the economy on FCOS would provide only little exchange value for the asset owners/producers if at all.

The prices for the end product customers are determined in the local markets. For example, a local e-commerce shop connects with the FCOS API, fetches product documentation (digital asset) and promotes it as a product to the local market. Then the “Fab Market Place”, which is the infrastructure for the local

market to operate, determines the price. The original designers/developers of the documentation only determine shares of the repository that is promoted in different markets across the globe.

The institutions of the global network and the local network each have efforts that are worth being compensated for. We propose that these efforts are made transparent in annual budgets. The respective controlling/supervising entity should have agency over the budget. Once the budget is confirmed, the respective sales for that time period are estimated. Then a share per sales on FCOS is calculated that is added to/subtracted from the prices to gain the budget needed to provide, develop and maintain FCOS.

5 The Economic Governance of Fab Cities and Regions

For describing the economic governance in Fab Cities, we first differentiate two spheres, which is in line with the Data-in-Data-out Fab City Vision:

- The local level - meaning each Fab City or Region: material flows.
- The global level - represented by the FCF and its bodies (collective, fc network, etc.) and an FCOS development organisation which is interwoven with the FCF: digital flows.

Figure 1: Infographic - Fab City OS (Fab City Hamburg Association, 2021)

5.1 The Local Sphere

In the local sphere, ideally, each fab city or region will have a local legal entity that is controlled by the actors of the local network (Commons-governance) by law of the respective legal/regulatory system the city or region finds itself in. This can be an association or a comparable organisation that is ruled by the local Fab City community by law of the organisation’s statutes (Decidim may also/alternatively play a role here). The local legal entity shall host a FCOS node upon which the local sphere of the Fab Economy unfolds. Because even though the basic source code of FCOS is not developed by the Fab Cities themselves, operating and administering a local node gives a rich set of possibilities to govern or steer the transactions that the node is used for by the local network. One of the most powerful decisions local FCOS nodes can enact is, at least for some applications, to decide on who can and who cannot participate in applications.

With regards to prices on the local level, we highlight that circulating atoms locally (in Fab Cities, material flows of a circular economy) has significantly higher marginal costs than circulating/reproducing/copying

bits has. Therefore, the economic governance on the local level is one where economic transactions are not executed for free, but people shall be able to make a living from it. For example, the effort a manufacturer has for manufacturing a product - even if its design was sourced for free - is worth being compensated by the customer via a software such as the marketplace application of FCOS.

We also count the distributed design process, which are inventions and their uploads as new or contributions to existing designs, as part of the local level. This is mainly because distributed OSH development is, to a large degree, a physical and up till now mostly human-guided process. So there usually is a local person that designs and often also develops a physical prototype, for which he or she make(s) a documentation. Tendentially, the more significant a contribution to an existing design is, the more likely the contributor has a physical derivative of the original digital source. So, the distribution of the design process is itself resource intensive, if compared to Wikipedia for example. In sum, distributed design has high marginal costs so the argumentation about governance and prices from the paragraphs above applies.

In terms of the overall economic governance system on the local level, FCOS does not enable peer production, because the transaction costs here cannot be reduced sufficiently in the foreseeable timespan. So locally, the Fab Economy that shall unfold on top of FCOS is a local market and circular economy that is competitive - only possible because it is fed - by a global digital commons of designs. We therefore call the economic governance in the local sphere a commons-enabled market and circular economy. Still, as the tools of and access to digital fabrication develop(s), also the transaction and marginal costs of production on top of FCOS decrease. So, in the very long run, we see a tendency towards peer production in the local realm.

5.2 The Global Sphere

In the global sphere, the existing Fab City network can be understood as a federation of Fab Cities and Regions. There is no single entity in the network that controls everything. FCOS reflects this; it is designed as a federated software network. Each Fab City and Region shall host its own FCOS node/instance and thereby be sovereign over the data it needs to produce locally. Another positive effect of FCOS and its products being open source or source available is that information asymmetry in the overall economy is reduced. This decreases passive rents, comparatively the most on the global level, but also on the local level.

The digital resources - shared and co-produced in and by the global federated network of FCOS nodes - are understood as a digital commons. The economic governance in the global realm in the medium term can therefore be described as commons-based peer production (compare with Benkler, 2002; Benkler, 2006). There will never be 100 % peer production, where all prices would theoretically be equal to zero, but peer production's share will increase with network size and density.

PITO to DITO

Figure 2: From Product-in-Trash-Out to Data-in-Data-out (Fab City Foundation, 2022)

6 Conclusion

To conclude, in this paper we propose an economic governance for the Fab Economy. We have done so to establish reasons, a direction and order for the development as well as outline possible implications of the deployment of Fab City OS, the digital infrastructure upon which that economy shall unfold. Specifically, the economic governance of Fab Cities and Regions is to be differentiated between a local physical realm and a global digital realm. In the global digital realm, we see a realistic chance for commons-based peer production to become the dominant economic governance model in the middle term. We have argued for this twofold. 1) because the essential economic transaction here is copying digital resources which have near zero marginal costs and should therefore be almost free. 2) The technology at hand with FCOS leads to a significant reduction of transaction costs which enables smaller economic actors to sustain and/or emerge. A precondition for Commons-based peer production in the global realm are better and more accessible digital and physical tools for digital design and fabrication as well as high network effects through a large and dense network of FCOS nodes and users.

In the local physical realm, we argue for a commons-enabled circular market economy to be the best economic governance. Analogous to the arguments above, we say that 1) because the Fab Economy in the local realm can only be a lot more physical, its marginal costs have to be higher and ergo higher prices are legitimate from a microeconomic perspective. 2) The transaction costs will be significantly higher than in the global realm, because more effort is involved in producing goods locally by people and physical machinery than in sharing bits/software worldwide.

Based on these insights on the economic governance of the Fab Economy, we have categorised and briefly outlined the different economic actors in the Fab Economy and their roles. In the light of this, we have proposed an institutional structure that reflects the differentiation of the governance spheres into a local and a global level.

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